

Interpersonal Communication in the Muhammadiyah Youth Organisation of Tombolopao Subdistrict, Gowa Regency

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Submission date: August 2025

Accepted date: October 2025

Published in: October 2025

Abstract:

This study examines the success of interpersonal communication in the Muhammadiyah Youth Organisation Branch in Erelembang Village, Gowa Regency. The study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with in-depth interviews with 12 informants, direct observation, and document analysis during September-November 2024. The results of the study found four methods of interpersonal communication that were applied: (1) repetition of messages that took advantage of close relationships in rural areas; (2) persuasion through two-way dialogue; (3) delivery of information with clear evidence of the benefits of organizing; and (4) a firm approach limited to members with specific characteristics. The success of communication was measured using five indicators that showed the creation of openness, mutual understanding, support, favorable responses, and equality in communication. The findings show that interpersonal communication is more successful than group communication in rural environments, with persuasion having the best impact. The contribution of this research lies in the development of an organisational communication model suitable for rural areas and an understanding of how to adapt communication methods to local characteristics.

Keywords: *interpersonal communication, youth organisations, communication success, rural communication, Muhammadiyah Youth.*

INTRODUCTION

Adapting interpersonal communication methods in religious organisations faces complex challenges when operating in diverse sociocultural contexts. Modern religious organisations are required to maintain the authenticity of traditional values while developing communication strategies that are responsive to local characteristics (McGuire, 2008). In the Indonesian context, geographical, social, and cultural heterogeneity necessitate religious organisations to develop adaptive and contextual communication approaches.

Communication sociology emphasises that the effectiveness of interpersonal communication does not solely depend on conformity with universal theory, but instead on the ability to adapt to the "cultural codes" and "social scripts" that apply in a particular community (Geertz, 1973; Hall, 1989). In the context of religious organisations, this adaptation becomes more complex

because it must consider spiritual dimensions, doctrinal values, and ritual practices that cannot be separated from the organisation's communication system (Berger, 2006).

Muhammadiyah Youth, as the largest autonomous organisation within the Muhammadiyah Association structure, faces particular challenges in adapting interpersonal communication methods. This organisation operates in more than 34 provinces with highly diverse sociocultural contexts, ranging from cosmopolitan urban to traditional rural areas (Nashir, 2010). Each context necessitates the development of different communication approaches to achieve effectiveness in cadre development and organisational cohesion maintenance.

The rural context in Indonesia has distinctive communication characteristics compared to urban settings. Redfield (1947) identified that folk (rural) communities have more personal communication patterns, based on strong kinship relations, and integrated with traditional value systems. Tönnies (2011), through the concept of *Gemeinschaft*, it explains that communication in rural communities tends to be more emotional, based on personal trust, and prioritises collective solidarity over instrumental efficiency.

Empirical studies on the adaptation of interpersonal communication methods in religious organisations in the rural context of Indonesia are still limited. Previous studies have tended to focus on normative analysis of religious organisational communication (Effendy, 2007) or comparative studies between organisations in urban settings (Wiryanto, 2004). This gap is significant considering that the majority of religious organisations in Indonesia operate in rural or semi-rural contexts with communication characteristics that differ from organisational communication theories developed in urban-industrial contexts.

The Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth in Erelembang Village, Tombolo Pao Subdistrict, Gowa Regency, offers an interesting case for understanding the adaptation of interpersonal communication methods in a rural context. This village has the distinctive characteristics of a rural community in South Sulawesi, with a social structure that is still steeped in traditional Bugis-Makassar values, limited access to communication technology, and the dominance of the agricultural sector in the community's economic structure. Nevertheless, the Muhammadiyah Youth organisation in this village shows positive dynamics in maintaining and increasing member participation.

The uniqueness of this context lies in how a modern organisation with a universal Islamic value system can adapt its interpersonal communication methods to operate effectively within the "local habitus" of rural communities (Bourdieu & Nice, 1977). This adaptation involves not only technical adjustments in communication, but also complex negotiations between universal Islamic values and local value systems, between formal organisational structures and traditional relationship patterns, and between universal *da'wah* objectives and the specific needs of local communities.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with descriptive research to analyse interpersonal communication in the Erelembang Branch of the Muhammadiyah Youth Organisation. The qualitative research method was chosen because it is in line with the research objective of gaining an in-depth understanding of the interpersonal communication methods applied in the organisation and their effectiveness in the sociocultural context of the rural community of Erelembang Village.

The research location was Erelembang Village, Tombolo Pao District, Gowa Regency, South Sulawesi. This location was selected purposively based on the consideration that the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth is a youth organisation that actively implements various interpersonal communication methods to maintain and increase member participation in the context of rural communities. Field research was conducted from September to November 2024 by conducting in-depth interviews and observations of the organisation's

activities during those three months to obtain comprehensive data on interpersonal communication practices in various situations and organisational activities.

Research informants were selected using purposive sampling techniques with the criteria of having direct knowledge and experience related to interpersonal communication in the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth. The informants consisted of the core administrators of the organisation, namely Sudirman Basri as the Chairman of the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth, Muh. Reski Pradana as an administrator, and several active members such as Fachri, Ilyas, and Khairul Akram. To obtain a broader perspective, the study also involved informants from outside the organisation, namely Drs. Abd Gani, as Chairman of the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah, and Putra Syarif, as Head of Erelembang Village, understand the dynamics of youth organisations in the village.

Data collection techniques were carried out through in-depth interviews using semi-structured interview guidelines focused on the interpersonal communication methods applied, the process of adapting communication to the local context, the challenges faced, and the effectiveness of interpersonal communication within the organisation. The interviews were conducted individually in various locations, as agreed with the informants, including at the Muhammadiyah Boarding School and the informants' homes, during the research period from September to November 2024. In addition to interviews, the study also used participant observation techniques to directly observe interpersonal communication practices in organisational activities and analyse organisational documents relevant to interpersonal communication, such as work programs, meeting minutes, and activity documentation.

Data analysis used qualitative descriptive analysis techniques with data reduction steps through sorting information relevant to the research focus, presenting data in the form of systematic narrative descriptions, and drawing conclusions based on data triangulation from various informant sources. The analysis process was carried out iteratively by comparing findings from interviews with various informants to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the interpersonal communication methods applied and their adaptation to the local context.

Data validity was ensured through source triangulation by involving various categories of informants, including administrators, members, and community leaders, who had different perspectives on interpersonal communication within the organisation. Member checking was carried out by confirming the interview results with several key informants to ensure the accuracy of the researcher's interpretation. The credibility of the research was also maintained through prolonged engagement by conducting in-depth interviews and sufficient observation over a period of three months to obtain a holistic understanding of the phenomenon of interpersonal communication within the Muhammadiyah Youth Organisation in Erelembang Branch.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Interpersonal Communication Methods of the Erelembang Branch of Pemuda Muhammadiyah

Interpersonal communication in rural youth organisations has unique dynamics compared to urban contexts. In Erelembang Village, Muhammadiyah Youth faces challenges specific to rural areas: limited access to technology, a majority of members who work as daily labourers with limited time, and a lack of understanding about the benefits of organising. These conditions require administrators to develop adaptive and contextual communication strategies. As stated by the Chair of the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth, "In carrying out organisational activities, we always strive to build communication with fellow administrators and new members. We apply various methods in communicating with members and administrators to improve cooperation and solidarity."

In a theoretical context, this study uses two main frameworks to analyse the communication process that occurs. First, Altman and Taylor's (1973) Social Penetration Theory, which explains

how interpersonal relationships develop gradually from a superficial level to a more intimate depth through self-disclosure and reciprocity. This theory is relevant for understanding how administrators build closeness with members through repeated and personal communication. Second, Petty and Cacioppo's (1986) Elaboration Likelihood Model, which identifies two pathways for processing persuasive messages: the central path through logical argumentation and the peripheral pathway through factors such as source credibility and emotional appeal.

Based on field data, the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth applies four different interpersonal communication methods according to the characteristics of its members and the situations they face. The first method is repetition, which takes advantage of the high frequency of social interaction in rural environments. The administrators consistently convey messages about the importance of youth participation in various informal contexts such as street gatherings, social events, and even home visits. Sudirman Basri explained,

"As administrators, we always take the time to talk with members of the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth, encouraging those who are already members to become active again, and inviting young people who have undergone training at IPM and settled in the village to join. We convey this message personally and repeatedly every time we meet with them so that they realise how important our invitation is."

The effectiveness of this method is evident from Fachri's response, who stated,

"The older members of Muhammadiyah Youth seem to take seriously the importance of our involvement as young people in the organisation. This is evident in how often they bring up discussions about the organisation whenever we meet."

This repetition method has significant advantages in a rural context because it utilises social structures that allow for natural and continuous interaction. However, this method also carries the risk of message fatigue if it is not managed with the right amount of variety. The administrators are aware of the importance of providing humorous interludes and choosing the right time to avoid boredom. The success of this method depends heavily on the communicator's ability to read the situation and adjust the intensity of the message to the atmosphere and context of the meeting.

The second method applied is a persuasive approach that prioritises two-way dialogue and provides space for members to express their concerns. This approach is in line with the concept of dialogic communication, which emphasises mutual understanding and reciprocity in the communication process. Muh. Reski Pradana explains its implementation: "I communicate persuasively with members who are rarely active, and the reasons they rarely attend are not only because they are busy with work but also because they feel they do not have an important role in the organisation, do not have space for expression, and are not given enough attention. Therefore, in my opinion, persuasive interpersonal communication is sometimes the best way to identify the problems faced by some members." This method has proven to be effective because it not only conveys messages but also listens to and responds to the specific needs of each individual.

The advantage of the persuasive method lies in its ability to create a sense of psychological security that allows members to open up about the obstacles they face. When members feel heard and understood, they tend to be more responsive to invitations to participate actively. Sudirman Basri added, "Usually, I invite my fellow members and village youth to have a light discussion about the importance of the role of youth in advancing our beloved village, and that in order to take action, we must unite, work together, and help each other for the greater good." This approach is also in line with the values of cooperation that are still strong in rural communities, so that messages about unity and cooperation are well received.

The third method is informative communication, which relies on presenting facts and concrete evidence about the benefits of organising. This approach is particularly relevant for

overcoming the scepticism of rural youth, who tend to be pragmatic and prioritise tangible benefits. As Sudirman Basri explained, "Establishing communication with rural youth about the importance of organisations is not as easy as one might think, because they are busy. They leave for work in the morning and only return in the afternoon, and sometimes they view organisations as useless. So, as organisation administrators, we sometimes convey the importance of organising to young people based on existing facts, such as recounting the achievements that people have gained through organising, broader relationships, and more open thinking through organising."

The effectiveness of the informative method lies in its ability to provide concrete evidence that reduces doubts about the value of joining an organisation. Leaders often use success stories from alums who have successfully developed their careers or businesses through the networks they built while participating in organisations. However, the limitation of this method is its focus on rational-cognitive aspects, while the motivation to participate in organisations also involves significant emotional and social dimensions. Therefore, the informative method is usually combined with the persuasive method to create a more comprehensive impact.

The fourth and most controversial method is the coercive or forceful approach, which is applied selectively and carefully. Sudirman Basri explains the reason: "Sometimes we do have to give forceful instructions to some members. However, we do not do this indiscriminately; we look at which members can be coerced and which members need to be approached persuasively. There are members whose inactivity is due to laziness, so we apply a little coercion for their own good." The use of this method shows that the administrators understand that intrinsic motivation is not always sufficient to encourage participation, and that sometimes external pressure is needed to break the initial inertia.

Although controversial, this coercive method has shown positive results in some cases. Khairul Akram testified about his experience: "Sometimes the administrators did exert a little pressure on some members. At first, I also felt that I was participating in the organisation because I was forced to. However, as time went on, I actually enjoyed getting together with other members to discuss, plan activities, or joke around. The effect of the organisation also made me more comfortable socialising with the people around me." This testimony shows that in specific contexts, enforced compliance can develop into identification and eventually internalisation, in accordance with Kelman's (1958) three-stage model of attitude change

However, the use of coercive methods must be critically evaluated because they carry significant risks. Excessive or misdirected coercion can cause psychological reactance and long-term resistance. Furthermore, this method contradicts the principles of ideal communication, which prioritise awareness and voluntariness. Therefore, organisations need to develop better persuasive communication skills so that dependence on coercive methods can be minimised.

A comparative evaluation of the four methods shows that the persuasive method produces the highest effectiveness because it can generate voluntary participation and long-term commitment. The repetition method ranks second because it is very suitable for rural contexts and easy to implement. The informative method is effective for sceptical targets but is limited to cognitive aspects. Meanwhile, the coercive method, although it shows results in some instances, has high risks and is only effective for certain characters.

The success of interpersonal communication by the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth also lies in their ability to adapt communication methods to the local context. They utilise social events such as weddings and community service as natural means of communication. Limited access to technology is not an obstacle because they optimise face-to-face communication, which is more personal and practical in a rural context. The integration of religious and social values in their messages also makes their communication more relevant to their audience.

Innovations developed by the organisation include a peer communication system in which active members are encouraged to become communicators for other members, a recognition system to reward members who actively communicate, and a multi-channel approach that combines face-to-face meetings with limited use of social media. However, there are still ongoing challenges, such as the limited number of administrators with optimal communication skills, competition for time with members' economic activities, and the need to develop more sophisticated methods.

Overall, the implementation of diverse interpersonal communication methods demonstrates a deep understanding of the complexity of the motivations and characteristics of youth organization members in a rural context. The organisation's success in retaining and developing members is highly dependent on flexibility in choosing communication methods, the ability to read individual characters and needs, and the skill of integrating local values into the communication process. The main lesson from this case is that the effectiveness of organizational communication does not lie in technological sophistication or structural formality, but in the quality of interpersonal relationships built through consistent, empathetic, and contextual communication.

2. Effectiveness of Interpersonal Communication in the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth

Interpersonal communication within the Erelembang Branch of Muhammadiyah Youth has a positive impact on member participation and engagement. This can be seen from the response of members who experienced increased motivation after interacting personally with administrators.

As stated by one informant:

"In my opinion, as a member of Muhammadiyah Youth, the interpersonal communication of the administrators is quite effective, because it builds familiarity. We are happy to attend activities because we feel valued. Organisations should always build interpersonal communication so that each member can be understood and their desires in the organisation can be understood."

This data shows that effectiveness is not only measured by the achievement of communication targets, but also by the relational dimension—the creation of closeness and a sense of being valued. To analyse this effectiveness more systematically, the study uses five dimensions of interpersonal communication according to DeVito (DeVito, 2000): openness, empathy, supportive attitude, positive attitude, and equality.

a. Openness: Creating a Safe Space for Dialogue

One measure of successful interpersonal communication is the willingness of members to be open about their personal challenges. Informant Fachri explained:

"Muhammadiyah administrators often encourage active participation in the organisation, so as a member, I feel I must be open about why I am rarely active in organisational activities. Sometimes I get solutions directly, and my enthusiasm to be active again grows because I feel cared for and considered important in the organisation."

What is interesting is the contrast between interpersonal communication and group communication:

"Interpersonal communication is very different from group communication. My friends in the Muhammadiyah Youth are more open in expressing their thoughts, ideas, and even criticism of the organisation's management, which we would not be able to get if we only communicated through open forums."

This phenomenon can be understood through the concept of psychological safety (Edmondson, 1999), where individuals feel safe to express themselves without fear of judgment. In an interpersonal setting, social pressure and embarrassment tend to decrease, making communication more authentic.

b. Empathy: Understanding the Perspectives of Members and the Organisation

Interpersonal communication also successfully builds mutual empathy between administrators and members. The data shows that through personal interaction, members begin to understand the challenges faced by the organisation:

"The interpersonal communication that we continue to build with several members, both new and long-standing, can, to a certain extent, foster a sense of caring for the organisation and an understanding of how overwhelmed the administrators are in carrying out activities when there is a shortage of human resources. As a result, some of them care about the condition of the organisation."

This process creates mutual understanding that encourages members to participate more, not only because they are asked to, but because they understand the organisation's needs. This is in line with the concept of perspective-taking in empathy literature, where the ability to understand other people's points of view is the basis for a more supportive response.

c. Supportive Attitude: Reducing Resistance and Enhancing Collaboration

An interpersonal communication approach has proven to be more effective in creating a supportive attitude than group communication:

"Through intensive communication with several members individually, they showed a supportive attitude compared to when discussions were held in groups. This supportive attitude was demonstrated by their frequent agreement with the arguments we presented."

This finding is interesting because it shows that the communication setting influences the audience's response. In interpersonal communication, the dynamics of defensive communication that often arise in groups tend to decrease, so that members are more receptive to the messages of the administrators.

d. Positive Attitude: Creating Reciprocal Positivity

The initiative of the administrators to visit members personally was perceived positively and triggered a similar response:

"Visiting members simply to encourage them to become active in the organisation again is a positive attitude shown by the Muhammadiyah Youth administrators, so I, as a member, also feel the need to respond with a positive attitude as well."

This data shows the occurrence of reciprocal positivity—the positive attitude of the administrators triggers a positive response from members, which then strengthens interpersonal relationships and improves the overall quality of organisational communication.

e. Equality: Reducing Hierarchy and Improving Accessibility

One important achievement of interpersonal communication is the reduction of hierarchical distance, which often hinders organisational communication:

"Interpersonal communication in this case, between us as administrators and members, will create a situation where new and long-time members will feel equal, so that they will not hesitate to raise issues they face during their time in the organisation. Because sometimes, they are reluctant to raise issues, not because they do not care, but because they are shy and consider the administrators to be in a higher position than them."

This phenomenon is important in the context of youth organisations where formal structures often create power distances that hinder bottom-up communication. Through interpersonal communication, these hierarchical barriers can be reduced.

The effectiveness of interpersonal communication in the Muhammadiyah Youth organisation cannot be separated from the socio-cultural context of rural areas, where values of personality and interpersonal closeness are still dominant. In this setting, formal and bureaucratic approaches tend to be less effective than personal and relational approaches.

Additionally, the relatively small size of youth organisations allows for intensive implementation of interpersonal communication, which may be challenging to apply in organisations with a larger number of members.

CONCLUSION

Based on a study of interpersonal communication in the Erelembang branch of the Muhammadiyah Youth Organisation, this research found that the organisation implements four methods of communication tailored to the characteristics of its members and the situations they face. The method of message repetition utilises close social relationships in rural areas to instil organisational values repeatedly in various informal settings. Persuasion through two-way dialogue and mutual understanding proved to be the most successful in generating voluntary participation and long-term commitment. Meanwhile, providing information with concrete evidence was effective in overcoming the doubts of rural youth about the benefits of organising. At the same time, a firm approach was applied cautiously to members with specific characteristics who were difficult to motivate.

The success of interpersonal communication in this organisation is evident through five mutually reinforcing dimensions. The creation of open communication has successfully reduced hierarchical barriers and enabled members to express personal constraints and offer constructive criticism. The mutual understanding between administrators and members creates a shared understanding of organisational challenges and individual obstacles. Mutual support is manifested in increased cooperation and reduced defensiveness in communication. Positive responses from members to administrators' initiatives create reciprocal relationships that strengthen organisational bonds. Equality in communication has successfully reduced the distance between superiors and subordinates, enabling more effective bottom-up communication.

This study also shows that interpersonal communication is more successful than group communication in the context of rural youth organisations. This is because interpersonal communication can create a sense of psychological security and accommodate the values of personal closeness that are still very strong in rural communities. The success of organisations in adapting their communication methods to local socio-cultural conditions is the primary key to effective communication.

Theoretically, this study reinforces the importance of the personal relationship dimension in youth organisation communication, especially in rural environments where closeness is as important as organisational goals. Practically, the findings of the study indicate the need to develop the interpersonal communication skills of administrators through regular training, structuring a personal approach so that it does not rely solely on individual initiative, and combining various communication methods to achieve optimal results. This research contributes to the development of an organisational communication model suitable for rural areas and enriches the understanding of the importance of adapting communication methods to local cultural characteristics.

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